

HOW DOES LACK OF SLEEP CAUSE VARICOSE VEINS?

The proper amount of sleep is very important for your health. If you are not getting it, then your body may go through stress. When you overlook pain, then it will become insufferable and lead you to severe vein conditions. If you are suffering from vein disease then it is not always possible that varicose veins and spider veins are visible on your legs.

Due to lesser distractions, symptoms of varicose veins are more noticeable at the end of the day. The work you do during day time causes leg pain and swelling which affects your sleep at night. The [vein doctor san jose](#) says that the cramps, swelling, and heaviness in your legs keeping you up till late at night.

According to the survey of **vein centers**, it is found that you need at least 7-8 hours of proper sleep. If you are getting the sleep of 5-6 hours then most probably you are at the risk of getting varicose veins. An ample amount of sleep can be considered good for your varicose veins.

During varicose veins, these positions help you in getting sleep

These are a few things you can do to relax your legs at night when you are having a varicose veins problem.

-Yoga and stretching help you in sleeping

For your vascular health and for varicose veins exercise is great but a **vein specialist** says doing yoga also does good. But you have to keep in mind that you shouldn't do this just

before bedtime. Doing general stretching before bedtime will help you to get good sleep. This helps in relaxing your muscles and improves blood circulation through the varicose veins.

-Keep your legs elevated

The [vein specialist san jose](#) recommends that you should elevate your legs to relieve the cramps and pain of varicose veins. You have to keep your legs at a level of 3-4 inches above the body. You can do this with the help of a folding towel or pillow. This will help in alleviating pressure from the legs. Sleeping in this position makes blood flow to the heart easier.

-Sleeping on your left side

The side you sleep in will also affect your sleep during varicose veins. **Vein doctor near me san jose** recommend you sleeping on your left side. It has been scientifically proven that you will get a good amount of sleep when you slept on your left side. Because sleeping on your left side relieves the pressure on your varicose veins. It helps in improving the blood circulation in the veins.

-Massage your legs

Before you go to bed, don't forget to massage your legs. For this, you can use some massage oils which help in massaging. Massage will improve blood circulation in varicose veins. It will provide you home based **varicose vein treatment**.

-Sleeping into a relaxing evening

You have to take a break between office hours. Your body needs to be relaxed a little bit in the evening. So don't go to bed immediately after active throughout the day. By doing this maybe you don't need any kind of **vein treatment**.